

MODELLING A HIGH RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY BY USING CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS ON FIVE LATENT CONSTRUCTS: VOLUNTEERISM PROGRAM

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Abstract-- This study aimed to evaluate the factor used to validate the best model of five latent constructs by using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on variables of volunteerism program. The data be collected through questionnaires distributed at four higher education institution. This questionnaire is constructed based on five dimension which is motivation, benefits, government support, barrier and challenges. The data were distributed by using stratified sampling technique and involving 453 respondents . In this case, the data were analyzed through four model which is model specification, model evaluation, model modification verification and model estimation by using Analysis Moment of Structural (AMOS) 18.0 in order to improve the the validity of each latent construct.. As a result showed that the realibility and validity of all latent construct is achieved.

Keywords: Stratified Sampling Technique, Volunteerism, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Realibility and Validity.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This study emphasized to validate the latent constructs by using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) through four model which is model specification, model evaluation, model modification

verification and model estimation. All of these models play a role to improve the fitness of latent construct which is more reliable and valid to remedy the multicollinearity problem. According to (Alias Lazim ,2011) explain when more than one indepedent variable apperas in modelling, it is possible that these variables are related to each other. Means that, the multicollinearity among variables or constructs is said to exist. According to (Hair et. al, 2006) explain CFA can be namely as the measurement model. In structural equation modelling (SEM), there are two types of model which is measurement model and structural model. The measurement model is frequently used nowadays among researchers to undergoes the CFA procedure In this case, this study apply CFA procedure before furthering the structural model in order to achieve the validity of latent contracts. First and foremost, the unidimensionality procedure should be apply for whole measurement model to remove the measuring items that have the lower standardized factor loadings (<0.50). According to (Zainudin, 2012) present the unidimensionality procedure is achieved when the measuring items have acceptable factor loadings for the respective latent construct. In order to achieve unidimensionality, the factor loading of items must be at least 0.50 for a newly developed scales and 0.60 for established scales.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Target Population

The target population for this study is among youth from the selected university which is majority of respondent age's must be between 15 to 40 years old. Since the university campuses are widely scattered in term of geographical location, the study applied the stratified sampling technique whereby in Terengganu only. Then, four higher education institution are selected randomly among the university available in Kuala Terengganu which is Universiti Malaysia Terengganu (UMT), Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM) Chendering, Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin (UNISZA), and Institut Pengajian Guru Batu Rakit (IPGBR). Thus, all students in the selected university are taken as respondents in the study. In other words, the number of students from both university that encompassed by variety faculty are as a population of the study.

2.2 The Measuring Instruments In The Study

The study adopts the questionnaires developed by emerged of the literature review based on the previous research, to measure the level of involvement in volunteerism program among youth. Hence, the variable of motivation is referring of level of involvement is measured to determine the relationship of variable that related with other variable such as benefits, challenges, barriers, and government support. Thus, the instruments was encompassed of five section provided for the respondents. Since this research is developed for the students from higher education institution, this study would customized the items accordingly an order to suit students in the education industry

3.0 THE PROCEDURE DATA ANALYSIS

3.1 Unidimensionality

Unidimensionality is the degree to which items load only on their respective constructs without having "parallel correlational pattern(s)" (Segars, 1997). Unidimensionality cannot be assessed using factor analysis or Cronbach alpha (Gerbing and Anderson, 1988, Segars, 1997). When there is unidimensionality, there is no significantly shared variance among the items beyond the construct which they reflect. In addition, while both methods of SEM provide for factor analysis, covariance-based SEM also provide the ability to compare alternative pre-specified measurement models and examine, through statistical significance statistics which is better supported by the data (Joreskog and Sorbom, 1989). The unidimensionality procedure can be classified as the model specification to specify

which one of the items would retain in the model by regarding on the factor loadings appear. Once the measurement model passes through the unidimensionality procedure, the discriminant validity and convergent validity are applied. Moreover, the fitness indexes also conducted in measurement model after passing through the unidimensionality procedure.

3.2 Model Estimation

Model estimation and statistical inference or hypothesis testing regarding the specified model and individual parameters are appropriate only if the sample is not too small for the estimation method chosen. According to Kline, 2005, a general rule of thumb is that the minimum sample size should be no less than 200 (preferably no less than 400 especially when an observed variable is not multivariate normally distributed). According to (Bollen, 1989) explain the estimation of a model may fail to converge or the solutions provided may be improper. In the former case, SEM software programs generally stop the estimation process and issue an error message or warning. In the latter, parameter estimates are provided but they are not interpretable because some estimates are out of range (e.g., correlation greater than 1, negative variance). These problems may result if a model is ill specified (e.g., the model is not identified), the data are problematic (e.g., sample size is too small, variables are highly correlated, etc.), or both. According to (Zainudin, 2012) proposed multicollinearity occurs when some variables are linearly dependent or strongly correlated (e.g., bivariate correlation $> .85$).

3.3 Model Evaluation

Once model parameter have been estimated, one would like to retain or reject the hypothesized model. This model can be classify as goodness of fit test. This procedure essentially a statistical hypothesis-testing problem, with the null hypothesis being that the model under consideration fits the data. There are 3 category of fitness which is incremental fits, absolute fits and parsimonious fits. The following table presented shows the type of fitness indexes with literature supported:

Name of Category	Name of Index	Index Full Name	Level of Acceptance	Literature
Absolute Fit	GFI	Goodness-of-fit Index	GFI > 0.90	Joreskog and Sorbom (1986)
	AGFI	Adjusted Goodness-of-fit test	AGFI > 0.90	Joreskog and Sorbom (1986)
	SRMR	Standardized root mean square residual	SRMR < 0.08	Bentler (1995)
	RMSEA	Root mean Square Error Approximation	RMSEA < 0.06	Steiger & Lind (1980)
Comment	Higher values of GFI and AGFI as well as lower value of SRMR and RMSEA indicate better model data fit.			
Incremental Fit	NFI	Normed Fit Index	NFI > 0.90	Bentler & Bonett (1980)
	TLI	Tucker Lewis Index	TLI > 0.95	Tucker and Lewis (1973)
	RNI	Relative noncentrality Index	Rni > 0.90	McDonald & Marsh (1990)
	CFI	Comparative Fit Index	CFI > 0.95	Bentler (1989,1990)
	IFI	Incremental Fit Index	IFI > 0.90	Bollen (1989)
Comment	Higher values of incremental fit indices indicate larger improvement over the baseline model in fit.			
Parsimonious Fit	Chisquare/Df	Chisquare/degree of Freedom	Chisq/Df < 5.0	Marsh and Hancock (1985)
Comment	Very sensitive to the sample size.			

Table 1: Type Fitness

3.4 Model Modification

This procedure is required when the model data is not fit after goes the model evaluation or goodness of fit model. Hence, the constraint should be apply in order to improve the fitness of model data. Besides, this procedure can remedy the multicollinearity problem. Basically, the multicollinearity exist when the correlation for each exogenous variable is so high. Based on the assumption for statistical, the error must be independent or not correlated each other. As a result, researchers are warned against making a

large number of changes and against making changes that are not supported by strong substantive theories (e.g., Byrne, 1998, p. 126). Changes made based on modification indices may not lead to the “true” model in a large variety of realistic situations (MacCallum, 1986; MacCallum, Roznowski, & Necowitz, 1992).

3.5 Discriminant validity

Discriminant validity means that a latent variable is able to account for more variance in the observed variables associated with it than a) measurement error or similar external, unmeasured influences; or b) other constructs within the conceptual framework. If this is not the case, then the validity of the individual indicators and of the construct is questionable (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity also known as shared variance. Shared variance is the amount of variance that a variable (construct) is able to explain in another variable (construct). It is represented by the square of the correlation between any two variables (constructs). For example, if the correlation between two variables, x_1 and x_2 is 0.7, then the shared variance between x_1 and x_2 is 0.49. If independent variables are correlated, they share some of their predictive power over dependent variables (Hair et al., 2006).

3.6 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

The AVE estimate is the average amount of variation that a latent construct is able to explain in the observed variables to which it is theoretically related. A latent construct A will correlate with observed variables, x_1 and x_2 , that theoretically relate to A. This correlation is generally referred to as a factor loading. If we square each of these correlations, this gives the amount of variation in each observed variable that the latent construct accounts for (i.e., shared variance). When this variance is averaged across all observed variables that relate theoretically to a latent construct, we generate the AVE (Farrell, 2009). . Fornell and Larcker (1981) present a method for assessing the discriminant validity of two or more factors. If the AVE for each construct is greater than its shared variance with any other construct, discriminant validity is supported.

$$\text{Average Variance Extracted (AVE)} = \sum K^2/n$$

The following table presented summarized the type of reliability and validity with literature supported. In the instance, the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) should be used to validate the measuring items in order to enhance the validity and reliability of measurement model before further the analysis.

Validity	Technique	Description
Construct Validity		
Convergent validity	CFA used in covariance-based SEM only	GFI>0.90, NFI>0.90, AGFI>0.9 and an insignificant χ^2 , to show unidimensionality. In addition, item loadings should be above 0.707, to show that over half the variance is captured by the latent construct (Chin,1998, Hair et. Al., 1998, Segars, 1997, Thompson et. Al., 1995).
Discriminant Validity	CFA used in covariance-based SEM only	Comparing the χ^2 of the original model with an alternative model where the constructs in question are united as a construct. If the χ^2 is significantly smaller in the original model, discriminant validity has been shown (Segars, 1997)
Convergent and discriminant validity	PCA used in PLS can assess factor analysis but not as rigorously as a CFA in LISREL does and without examining unidimensionality	Each construct AVE should be larger than its correlation with other constructs, and each item should load more highly on its assigned construct than on the other constructs.
Reliability		
Internal Consistency	Cronbach Alpha	Cronbach alpha should be above 0.60 for explanatory research and above 0.70 for confirmatory research (Nunnally, 1967, Nunnally, 1978, Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994, Peter, 1979)
	SEM	The internal consistency coefficient should be above 0.70 (Hair et al., 1998, Thompson et al 1995)
Unidimensionality Reliability	Covariance-based SEM only	Model comparison favor unidimensionality with a significantly smaller χ^2 in the proposed measurement model in comparison with alternative measurement models (Segars, 1997)

Table 2: Type Reliability and Validity

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS

By regarding on objective research, the CFA procedure is conducted. All measurement models must be validated and accepted prior to modelling the structural model. In this case, there are have 5 dimension which is motivation (16 items), challenges (6 items), government support (9 items), barrier (8 items), and benefits (14 items). According to Hair et.al, 2010, the factor loadings for each items should be greater than 0.6. However, factor loading which greater than 0.50 is also accepted depend on the decision by the researcher if have

strong reason not to do so. The table below shows the territory items results leave after remove:

Construct	Number of items before remove	Number of items after remove
Motivation	16	15
Benefits	14	11
Challenges	6	6
Barrier	8	4
Government Support	9	6

Table 3: Unidimensionality Result

Despite having the unidimensionality procedure, the model evaluation, model modification, and model estimation should be apply in order to obtain the exactly result. The model evaluation is consider as the goodness of fit model. The model evaluation can be obtained based on the Root Mean Square Approximation (RMSEA), Baseline Comparison (IFI, CFI, and TLI) and Chisquare over degree of freedom. The result can be obtained as the table presented below:

Variables	Chi/Squ	RMSEA	IFI	CFI	TLI
Type of fit	Parsimonous Fit	Absolute Fit	Incremental Fit		
Motivation	5.584	0.101	0.904	0.903	0.887
Benefits	7.028	0.115	0.899	0.898	0.876
Barrier	13.75	0.168	0.949	0.948	0.845
Challenges	11.067	0.149	0.916	0.915	0.859
Government Support	8.867	0.132	0.927	0.927	0.878

Table 4: Fitness Before Constraints

All variables are invalid since category for parsimonous fit and absolute fit is not achieved as the recommended of literature supported. Basically, the fitness of indexes cannot be acheived due to the multicollinearity problem. Based on the assumption of statistics, the variable should be independent or uncorrelated each other. Thus, the model modification is employed to remedy the multicollinearity problem. If the value of covariances is too high (>100.0), either one of the item should be dropped. In this case, the benefits has one pair of covariance (>100.0). Hence, the item with the lowest factor loading should be removed and respecify the measurement model of benefits. This procedure is important to help the researchers ascertain the best model. The table below show the result of fitness indexes after having the model modification verification:

Variables	ChiSqu/Df	RMSEA	IFI	CFI	TLI
Type of fit	Parsimonous Fit	Absolute Fit	Incremental Fit		
Motivation	2.209	0.052	0.978	0.978	0.970
Benefits	2.133	0.05	0.984	0.984	0.978
Barrier	1.093	0.014	1.000	1.000	0.999
Challenges	2.314	0.054	0.991	0.991	0.982
Government Support	3.700	0.077	0.981	0.980	0.958

Table 5: Fitness After Constraints

All of measurement model is valid since achieve the fitness of indexes after apply the constraints that represents for model modification. Then, the construct validity should be employed to validate the measurement models that consists of bivariate correlation (<0.85), and Average Variance

Extracted (AVE). If the bivariate correlation is greater than 0.85 among the exogenous variables, the researcher should choose either one to remove from the subsequent analysis. Means that, the highly bivariate correlation is having the same contribution among these variables.

Figure 1: Construct Validity

The figure above shows the structural model after evaluate the goodness of fit-test with value of correlation. This step is important to develop the discriminant validity for latent exogenous and endogenous variables. Hence, the constraint or double headed arrow is required to examine the strength correlation between these constructs.

		Estimate
Motivation	<-> Benefits	.690
Benefits	<-> Challenges	.219
Benefits	<-> Barrier	.287
Barrier	<-> Government_Support	.261
Challenges	<-> Barrier	.390
Motivation	<-> Challenges	.229
Challenges	<-> Government_Support	.277
Motivation	<-> Barrier	.297
Motivation	<-> Government_Support	.449
Benefits	<-> Government_Support	.451

Table 6: Correlation Result

By regarding on the table above, all these constructs shows the correlation measure are below 0.85. Thus, the discriminant validity is achieved and all of these construct could be use in a structural model for futher analysis. According to (Zainudin 2012) if the measure correlation between two exogenous variables is higher than 0.85, one can conclude that the discriminant validity is not achieve acceptance. In this case, the construct are redundant of each other. Therefore, either one of these construct must be drop in the subsequent

analysis.

Construct	Items Loadings	Factor Loading	Cronbach Alpha	CR	AVE
Benefits	B1	0.636	0.923	0.898	0.503
	B3	0.669			
	B4	0.711			
	B5	0.775			
	B6	0.811			
	B7	0.772			
	B9	0.643			
	B10	0.726			
	B11	0.824			
	B12	0.776			
	B14	0.644			
	Motivation	M1			
M2		0.783			
M3		0.755			
M4		0.777			
M5		0.799			
M6		0.809			
M7		0.569			
M8		0.702			
M10		0.777			
M11		0.742			
M12		0.715			
M13		0.634			
M14		0.767			
M15		0.709			
M16		0.698			
Challenges		C1	0.688	0.849	0.844
	C2	0.798			
	C3	0.595			
	C4	0.748			
	C5	0.721			
	C6	0.635			
Barrier	Bar1	0.627	0.761	0.758	0.452
	Bar2	0.765			
	Bar3	0.775			
	Bar4	0.522			
Government_Support	G1	0.688	0.835	0.838	0.467
	G2	0.798			
	G3	0.595			
	G4	0.748			
	G5	0.721			
	G6	0.635			

Table 7: Convergent Validity

4.1 Convergent Validity

According to Fornell and Larcker, 1981 proposed three procedures to asses for convergent validity of the measurement items which is include tradisional method (cronbach alpha), composite reliability (CR), and the average variance extracted (AVE). According to Nunally & bernstein, 1994 explore the Cronbach Alpha with a value of 0.7 or higher being recommended.

4.1 Discriminant Validity

According to Fornell et.al, 1982 proposed discriminant validity is present when the variance shared between construct and any other construct is

Benefits	Motivation	Challenges	Barrier	Government_Support
0.709				
0.690	0.721			
0.219	0.229	0.691		
0.287	0.297	0.390	0.672	
0.451	0.449	0.277	0.261	0.683

Table 8; Discriminant Validity

the model is less than the variances that construct shares with its indicators. The result for discriminant validity is presented as below:

The diagonal value is higher than in its row and column. The diagonal values with bold are the square root of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) while other value are the correlation between the respective construct from pooled confirmatory factor analysis.

5.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Using the factor volunteerism as a research model, the findings revealed all the reliability and validity of measurement model which is CFA procedure is achieved. The CFA procedure is very important before furthering the analysis. Hence, the reliability and validity applied to remedy the multicollinearity

problem besides to improve the fitness of measurement model. The better model is depend on the fitness indexes of measurement model. Thus, the requirement for unidimensionality, validity and reliability needs to be addressed prior to modelling the structural model.

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